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González-Prida, V., Gómez, J., & Crespo Márquez, A. (2011).
Practical application of an Analytic Hierarchy Process for the improvement of the
warranty management.

Journal of Quality in Maintenance Engineering, 17(2), 163–182.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/13552511111134592>

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